

Effectiveness of Ligation of Inter Sphincteric Fistula Tract (LIFT) In the Management of Fistulas in Ano in Telangana PopulationV Bhaskara Reddy K¹, Sontam V. Prasada Reddy²¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Mallareddy Institute of Medical Sciences Suraram, Hyderabad, Telangana-500055.²Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Mallareddy Institute of Medical Sciences Suraram, Hyderabad, Telangana-500055

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Abstract:**Background:** Fistula in ano is an abnormal communication between epithelized surface of anal canal and perianal skin ligation of the intersphincteric fistula tract. This is a new sphincter-saving method with good results without recurrence.**Method:** 95 adult patients were confirmed to be competent for surgery. USG examination having a 7 to 10 MHZ transducer passed into the anal canal, which is carried out with the patient in a left lateral position. Serial radial images were taken to study the location and position of the fistula. The LIFT procedure was similar to the Rojanaskul proposed method. The duration of surgery and healing time were also noted.**Results:** The study of classification included Parks classification. It has 83 (87.3%) were Trans Sphincteric, 9 (9.4%) intersphincteric, 3 (3.1%) suprasphincteric, Classification on basis of course has 35 (36.8%) anterior straight, 48 (50.5%) posterior straight, 9 (9.4%) curved, and 3 (3.1%) semi-horseshoes. Classification on the tract had 86 (90.5%) single tracts and 9 (9.47%) multiple tracts. Operating time was 35.2 (\pm 3.30), intersphincteric wound healing 23.20 (\pm 4.10), external wound healing 25.80 (\pm 63.80).**Conclusion:** The LIFT technique is an ideal minimally invasive technique with a high rate of rapid healing and without any resultant of incontinence.**Keywords:** Park's classification, MHz transducer, Vicryl suture, Crypto-glandular infection.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Fistula means pipe or tube in Latin. It is an abnormal communication between the epithelized surface of anal canal and usually the perianal skin. Fistula in ano has been a common surgical ailment reported since the time of Hippocrates, but little evidence exists on its management [1]. A fistula in ano is a benign, treatable lesion of the rectum and anal canal. Cryptoglandular infections are observed in 90% of cases.

The majority of the infections are acute, and a minority contributed by chronic, low-grade infections; hence, it has various etiologies. The pathogenic is characterized by bursting open of an acute or improperly treated anorectal abscess into the perianal skin. Infection developed in the anal gland lying within the sub-mucosa of the anal canal is the direct cause of most of the fistula in ano [2]. It may be associated with tuberculosis, Crohn's disease, and malignancies under such conditions. It becomes a surgical challenge for both patients and surgeons [3]. There are variable procedures for the management of anal fistula with variable risk of

incontinence and recurrence, which include fistulotomy, set on placement endo-rectal advancement flap, ano-cutaneous advancement flat excision, and closure of the internal opening [4].

Hence, an attempt is made to evaluate and manage the fistula in ano.

Material and Method

95 adult patients regularly visiting the surgery department at Mallareddy Institute of Medical Sciences Suraram, Hyderabad, and Telangana-500055 were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: Patients above the age of 20 yearly, recently diagnosed complex perianal fistulas of infective etiology were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with superficial fistula, recurrent fistula, recurrent fistula secondary to tumor in inflammatory bowel disease, TB or trauma, pre-existing incontinence, or extra-sphincteric fistula immune compromised patients were excluded from study.

Method:

The detailed history was collected from every patient demographic, type of fistula, the extent of sphincter involvement, the location of external and internal openings, the presence of multiple tracts, tract collection, and perianal or submucosal collection. Every patient had an anal ultrasound examination. It involves the passage of 7 to 10 MHz transducer into the anal canal, which is carried out with the patient in the left lateral position.

Operative techniques:

Patients were prepared with evacuation enema 6–8 hours before the time of operation. All operations were performed under regional anesthesia. Broad-spectrum antibiotics and metronidazole were given before operation.

The position of the patient was lithotomy, where the external opening of the fistula lies anteriorly, and prone Jack-knife with the buttocks strapped apart, where the external opening of the fistula lies posteriorly. A detail of the LIFT procedure is similar to that proposed by Rojanasakul et al. 2007 [5].

The first internal opening was identified by palpation or by injection of saline through an external opening. A curvilinear incision was made in the intersphincteric groove over the site of the internal opening. The intersphincteric plane was dissected by scissor and diathermy meticulously until the fibrous fistulous tract was identified.

Once the tract was identified, it was then transfixated with 2/0 vicryl close to the internal sphincter. Saline was injected through the external opening to confirm that the tract was no longer patent, and it was then divided distal to the point of ligation. After traction, a segment of the distal tract was excised. From the external opening, the tract was

opened, curetted, and washed with 10% povidone iodine solution. Finally, the intersphincteric incision wound was repaired with an interrupted 2/0 Vicryl suture.

Post-operative management and follow-up:

Post-operatively, antibiotics were given for gram-negative organisms and anaerobes for 5 to 7 days. Analgesics were given according to patient's needs. Patients were discharged with antibiotics, analgesics, stool softener, and advice to take a sitz bath. Patients were asked to come after 1 week of operation for stitch removal of intersphincteric wound. The subsequent follow-up consultation was weekly after the first visit till complete wound healing. At each visit, patients were interviewed for pain, discharge, wound healing, and clinical continence status. On examination, intersphincteric incision wound, site of previous external and internal opening of fistula, and sphincter tone were assessed. After healing, the patients were asked to visit if any recurrent pain, swelling, or discharge occurred. Clinical healing was defined as healing of intersphincteric and external opening wounds, absence of fistula drainage, and no evidence of abscess formation at any time during follow-up. Recurrence was defined as a non-healing wound 6 weeks after surgery or reappearance of an external opening, persistent discharge, or reappearance of a fistula after the initial wound had healed. The duration of the study was December 2022 to August 2023.

Statistical analysis:

Fistulae of different types were classified with percentage. The duration of surgery and healing was compared with the z test. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of male and female was 3:1.

Figure 1: Repairing the fistula tract: the right one next to the edge of the internal sphincter and the left is by the external sphincter

Figure 2: the second step of the technique, with correct identification of the fistula tract

Figure 3 (a): the tract was transfixed close to the internal sphincter with 2/0 vicryl and divided distal to the point of ligation

Figure 3 (b): partial core-out fistulectomy performed from the external opening to the outer border of the external sphincter

Figure 3 (c): the intersphincteric tract, identified by meticulous dissection and hooked using a vascular loop, was confirmed by passing a probe

Observation and Results

Table-1: Classification and characteristic of fistula

- a) Park’s classification: 83 (87.3%) trans-sphincteric, 9 (9.4%) Inter-sphincteric, 3 (3.1%) supra-sphincteric
- b) Classification based on the course of fistula: 35 (36.8%) anterior straight, 48 (50.5%) posterior

straight, 9 (9.4%) curved, 3 (3.1%) semi horse-shoe

- c) Classification based on the tract: 86 (90.5%) single tract, 9 (9.47%) multiple tracts.

Table-2: Duration of surgery and wound healing: 35.2 (±3.30) operating time (minutes) 23.20 (±4.10) Inter-sphincteric wound healing, 25.80 (±6.80) external opening wound healing (in days).

Table 1: Study of classification and characteristics of fistulae

Classifications of Fistulae	Number	Percentage %
(a) Park’s classification		
Trans–sphincteric	83	87.3
Intersphincteric	9	9.4
Supra sphincteric	3	3.1
(b) Classification based on the course of fistulae		
Anterior Straight	35	36.8
Posterior Straight	48	50.5
Curved	9	9.4
Semi horse-shoe	3	3.1
(c) Classification based on the tract		
single tract	86	9.5
Multiple tract	9	9.47

Figure 4: Study of classification and characteristics of fistulae

Table 2: Duration of surgery and wound healing

Variations	Mean value (SD±)
(a) Operating time (minutes)	35.2 (± 3.30)
(b) Intersphincteric wound healing (days)	23.20 (± 4.10)
(c) External opening wound healing (days)	25.80 (± 6.80)

Figure 5: Duration of surgery and wound healing

Discussion

Study of effectiveness of ligation of intersphincteric sphincteric Fistula tract (LIFT) in the management of fistula in ano in Telangana population. In the classification and characteristics of fistulae (a) In Parks classification had 83 (87.3%) intersphincteric, 9 (9.4%), intrasphincteric, and 3 (3.1%) suprasphincteric. (b) The classification based on the course of fistulae had 35 (36.8%) anterior straight, 48 (50.5%) posterior straight, 9 (9.4%) curved, and 3 (3.1%) semi-horseshoe. (c) Classification based on tract: 86 (90.5%) had a single tract, 9 (9.47%) had a multiple tract (Table 1).

The duration of surgery and wound healing was 35.2 (± 3.30) minutes was operation time, 23.20 (± 4.10) days was intra intersphincteric healing wound, 25.80 (± 6.80) days was external opening wound healing (Table 2). (Figures 1, 2, and 3) These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [6,7,8].

LIFT technique was developed in 2007 by Arun Rojana Sakul et al. at Bangkok, Thailand. The central idea of this procedure is that the excision of and ligation of the intersphincteric tract can occlude the entry of fecal particles in the fistula and, at the same time, eliminate the septic focus intersphincteric. This could result in the cure of anal canal [9]. Now days there is a growing interest in ligation of LIFT

because the procedure is minimally invasive, easy to learn and perform, and can be used on recurrent cases. The early results of the LIFT procedure were quite impressive, with success rates ranging from 57% to 97% with minimal morbidity and little or no impact on continence status. Some surgeons have used modifications of LIFT by combining it with additional procedures such as trans-anal advancement flaps or bioprosthetic prosthetic plug [10]. The healing rate improved to 95% in the LIFT with anal fistula plug procedure but did not improve with the combination of advancement flap.

Another advantage of the LIFT procedure is that it can be performed in cases of recurrence even when failure occurred with previous use of the LIFT technique [11]. Recurrence of anal fistula is mainly due to infection and technical errors. Infection was one of the reasons for non-healing of internal opening wounds because it is caused by the breakdown of the closure wound on the internal sphincter. So in cases with persistent anal abscesses or infected incisional wounds, infection could be a factor for treatment failure.

Summary and Conclusion

Ligation of the intersphincteric fistula tract (LIFT) has a high success rate in primary or recurrent complex fistulae-in-ano. Recurrence is related to diabetes mellitus, perianal collections, abscess

along the tract, and multiple tracts. It can be successfully managed by repeated LIFT.

Limitation of study:

Due to the tertiary location of the research center, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

This research paper is approved by the ethical committee of Mallareddy Institute of Medical Sciences Suraram, Hyderabad, and Telangana-500055.

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